

MODERN APPROACHES TO TEACHING TEXTBOOKS OF NEW GENERATION IN PRIMARY EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract. *Organizational pedagogical characteristics of primary school students based on the international evaluation program are discussed. The author mentions modern methods of developing life skills in the XXI century: 1. "Bloom's taxonomy" 2. "Venn diagram" 3. "Torrent's test" 4. "Six bags" 5. "Problem situations" 6. "Busen".*

Keywords: *new project, essential knowledge, effective communication, 21st century skills, international studies, grammar literacy, team members.*

*The boy who is reading in the library today can
control ten children watching TV tomorrow
Shavkat Mirziyoyev*

INTRODUCTION

In this article, in order to ensure the implementation of the order of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 25 of January 17, 2022 "On approval of the regulation on the procedure for creating a system of improving the qualifications of public education workers" and the order of the Minister of National Education No. 121 of April 20, 2022 "On approval of state education requirements", introduction of modern principles of personnel policy formation into the system of general secondary education through the implementation of advanced and open organizational and legal mechanisms for improving the qualifications of pedagogical personnel, attention to content writing based on the professional standards of general secondary school teachers is one of the priority tasks, and it is primary based on modern requirements aims to improve the content of continuous professional development processes in education, to systematically improve their professional competence.

Enlightenment scholar Thomas Fawell Buxton said, "Life experience shows that success is achieved not by ability, but by hard work." "A person who works hard will definitely be a winner," he said, adding that any professional can work hard on himself while improving his knowledge and skills. All stages of the education sector are radically reformed and being developed comprehensively, the fourth priority direction in the development strategy of the country is aimed at the development of the education sector and human capital. On December 29, 2022, at the 24th International Congress Center, the Head of State said "Increasing the quality of education is the only right way to develop New Uzbekistan!" and got acquainted with the exhibition of modern textbooks on the subject. An important factor in improving the quality of education and making children interested in reading books is, first of all, creating a good textbook. In the concept of development of the public education system until 2030 approved by the Decree of the Head of State No. 5712 of April 29, 2019, the tasks of improving the teaching methodology were determined.

Accordingly, textbooks have been updated over the last four years, and a special working group has prepared textbooks for grades 1-4 based on advanced foreign methodology. In 2023, the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 international license issued within the framework of USAID/Uzbekistan's "Educational Program for Improvement" is aligned with the original version. Before introducing a new innovative approach to schools of Uzbekistan, the best practices in the field of education of foreign countries such as Singapore, China, England, Finland, Estonia are studied, and students are given the opportunity to develop 21st century skills that include the principle of "4C". In the field of education of countries that have high positions in international ratings such as PISA, PIRLS, special attention is paid to skills such as communication, research and creativity, including the principle of "4C" among students.

To sum up, it is good that our society has great financial resources, capable of accepting and mastering any innovation, new project, new technology that appears in the world. That's why we want the main strategies in the field of education to be based on mastering traditional teaching methods that increase student's thinking ability and provide quality education along with mastering new technology.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Organizational pedagogical characteristics of primary school students based on the international evaluation program.

Appendix 1: Rules for working in small groups: students must have the necessary knowledge and skills to perform the work. Specific tasks should be given to the groups. Sufficient time will be allocated to complete the task set before the small group. It should be noted that comments in groups are not limited and should not be suppressed. They should clearly know how to present the results of the group; the teacher should guide them. Anyway, get involved, feel free to express your opinion.

Appendix 2: Questions to stimulate student learning. 1. What is the development of students' functional literacy? 2. What does international research provide? 3. Name the 21st century skills.

Appendix 3: Development of students' functional literacy: together - start, together - progress and work together - success!

Our goal: to introduce innovative pedagogical technologies, effective forms and methods of teaching into the educational process; continuous improvement of the professional skills of teachers and help to effectively prepare for the next stage of research of the international assessment program

Tasks: providing educational process using innovative methods based on modern requirements in general secondary education organizations; addressing student achievement gaps in math, reading, and science in international assessment program research; teaching students logical thinking and effective communication, methods aimed at finding solutions to life problems; identify, publish and support exchange of best practices of teaching staff.

What is functional literacy? Being able to use the knowledge and skills acquired at school in life, that is, educational results that can be achieved during school education, being able to solve life problems in its various areas. Mathematical literacy is a person's ability to think mathematically about various life situations (contexts) and problems, to be able to express a given problem with the help of mathematics, to be able to use and implement mathematics in solving problems. Results obtained to explain and evaluate the solution to the problem.

Natural-scientific literacy means a person's knowledge of ideas related to natural sciences, ability to solve problems related to natural sciences as an active citizen. A literate person in the natural sciences can participate in the discussion of issues related to natural sciences and technologies based on scientific evidence. Phet simulations of the University of Colorado Boulder, USA (phet simulations, 2002) - mathematics, chemistry, physics, biology, geography - more than 168 free interactive simulations translated into 121 languages, including: Uzbek - 111; Russian - 91; Kazakh language - 80; 38 Tajik language; Turkmen language - 100. Functional Literacy Development Resource (Physics Aviation, 2013) - provides in-depth analysis of physics, chemistry and mathematics in English, interactive lessons, online resources, simulation games, including labs, equipment use and games.

A resource for the development of students' functional literacy: to make students aware of scientific achievements, to make independent decisions that solve problems related to the environment and human health, to protect natural resources, to be able to use the knowledge they have acquired. In life situations, it plays an important role in developing their skills, such as learning, being able to react to nature and social phenomena, preparing for life and increasing their interest in modern professions.

Our plan ... In cooperation ... To introduce innovative pedagogical technologies, effective forms and methods of training into educational process; to help teachers successfully participate in the next phase of research in international assessment programs by continuously improving their professional skills. Distinctive Aspects of Mathematical Literacy Development: Who Conducts the Research? — the PISA study is conducted by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). The survey was first conducted in 2000 and is conducted once every 3 years. Why are pisa surveys conducted every three years?

The main task of PISA is to provide member countries with information on education policy, support in decision-making. Conducting the survey every three years provides countries with timely information, including information and analysis that takes into account the impact of policy decisions and related programs. What does Uzbekistan's participation in these studies bring? - to determine the readiness of general education school students to continue the next stage of education, as well as independent life; determination of priority directions for improvement of general secondary education; you can get comparative information about the educational achievements of students, as well as about the educational system of different countries.

Research Background: In the mid-1990s, Eidu began work on the Program for International Assessment (PISA) in order to obtain reliable information about the knowledge and skills of students and the effectiveness of the education system. PISA was officially launched in 1997. 1. 2000 2.2003 3.2006 Research will be conducted in 2025, 2028 and 2031. Mathematical Literacy: An International Assessment Program mainly addresses the following questions: How prepared are young people to overcome the obstacles they will face in their future lives? Are students able to analyze, search, determine the causes of conflicts and express their thoughts? At what level is the ability of students to apply the acquired knowledge and skills in life situations? Mathematical Literacy in the Pisa International Study: Components and Actions of Competence; 21st century skills; mathematical literacy; mathematical reasoning and problem solving.

Recommendations: What international studies have our students participated in to assess reading literacy? Uzbekistan's participation in international research (reading literacy) PIRLS 2021: an international research program to assess the level of reading comprehension of primary

school students. 5948 4th grade students in 57 regions of Uzbekistan; 180 educational institutions. 437 (2.9) ranks 49th among the bottom 10 countries. PISA 2022: 81 participants, 7293 15-year-old students, 202 educational institutions across Uzbekistan took part in the international program for assessing students' literacy. What is Uzbekistan's place in reading literacy? 336 points among the bottom 10 countries.

RESEARCH RESULTS

"THINKING IS THE CORRECT AND NOBLE WAY OF KNOWLEDGE CALCULATED" CONFUCIUS

Development of writing, speaking skills in improving students' reading literacy. PIRLS is an example of international studies conducted every 5 years by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievements (IEA). The study assesses the academic achievement of elementary school students by conducting objective tests on students selected as representatives of this class, rather than on all students. Also, surveys of school principals, teachers, students, and even parents are conducted and valuable information is gathered about the factors affecting the quality of education. Literacy - 400-500 words for countries with low literacy, the ability to understand and use the types of written language required by society and used by people; in PIRLS it is about 1000 words; clarity and consistency are important criteria.

Problematic issues in the implementation of PIRLS tasks based on international experience in elementary grades: low logical thinking and creativity of students, inability to use additional literature when working with the text. Lack of assignments on creativity, critical thinking and problem situations in class. Students read the meaning of the text, misunderstanding, poor work on the text. Lack of ability to explain, synthesize, turning the reading work into written speech, and writing one's opinion based on correct and completely accurate information. Integrative, action-oriented, conscious, inventive, diverse and critical perspectives should also be considered.

Grammatical literacy is the importance of expanding the student's vocabulary, feeling and understanding the intricacies of word meanings, differences and similarities, being able to speak and write correctly, connecting words and sentences, composing a text, correctly evaluating speech situations, the importance of forming and educating the skills of appropriate use of language opportunities.

Reading literacy - raising to the level of a thoughtful, creative reader; expanding knowledge about the environment, existence, enriching worldview through reading; formation of simple literary concepts in thinking; reading and understanding text in any style, improving critical and creative thinking skills. Familiarize oneself with texts from various fields in all styles and develop one's written speaking through exercises and tasks.

Discussions. *Modern methods of developing life skills in the XXI century: 1. "Bloom's taxonomy" 2. "Venn diagram" 3. "Torrent's test" 4. "Six bags" 5. "Problem situations" 6. "Busen".*

"Bloom's pie" - 1. Simple questions 2. Clarifying questions. 3. Explanatory questions. 4. Creative questions. 5. Evaluation questions. 6. Practical questions. What are common questions? Where? Clarifying questions - "you say..." "if I understand you correctly..." "I may be wrong, but you said..." creative questions - "if... What would you do?" "if... What do you think will happen?" evaluation questions - "why this is negative and this is positive?". "how is this different from that?" practical questions - "how can this be used?" "What can be done in such cases?".

Talk about bagels - conversation Do you like bagels? What aspects do you like or dislike? Name three of its characteristics. Do you think he did the right thing by running away from home?

Does he leave home because he is bored? What do you think Boursak would do? Does he know what awaits him? Are you ready for life on the street or in the woods? Did he manage to trick the rabbit? Is he out of danger? Does he know that this is how he will get away with it next time? Do you think the bagel managed to trick the wolf? Is he out of danger? Does he know that this is how he will get away with it next time? Did he manage to trick the rabbit? Is he out of danger? Does he know that this is how he will get away with it next time? Is the fox as simple as Boursak thinks? What do you think, like a rabbit, a bear, a wolf, the fox will be fooled by the bagel's words?

Boursak was happy that he was deceiving everyone, what happened now? Where did Boursak go wrong? Do such situations happen in our lives? (there are those who go out without their parents' permission and go down a path they don't know) will they end up in trouble?

"Buyzen" method - write down what daily activities you can use these things in life, apart from their function. For example: a ladder, a cup, a pen. Torrens Test - Draw these symbols, translate them into words and analyze them.

"Venn Diagram" - Gerda, Snow Queen and their similarities. word-to-word exercise - find words or phrases found in fairy tales for the word "fairy tales" from the letters below. E--- country, man, bravery, pride, brave prince... R--- knight... T--- turtle, fox, bald boy, scale, tyrant... E--- patriotic king ... G--- a flower, a flower, a flower...

The "Secret Communication" Method: Each week, let one passive, slow-absorbing student in your class know that you will pay more attention to them during the week. The student inevitably develops self-confidence, inner strength, and begins to be active in class with good posture. Prepares for your lesson.

Working with synonyms: synonyms are big, great, big, huge, giant, impressive, the word big means wide, it is also used for the specific concept. An abstract concept. The words "great", "leader", "strong", "abyarly" and "abyat" are used for things that are very large in size, and the words "giant", "large" are used for very large things. Large is rarely used. Giant is typical of the book style and is mainly used for location and construction. Task examples: choose the word that has the meaning for the given word. The teacher says the words "heaven" in the past noun, "tasty" in the past adjective, and "learn" in the past tense of the verb. Students choose synonyms for the following words: sky - blue, space, cosmos; delicious - sweet, pleasant; to get used to - to learn, to get used to, to become a habit. Comparing the meanings of the words in the phrase: the clock went, the train went, my brother went; highway, hard heart; silver spoon, silver winter.

Logical exercises: distinguishing objects from given objects that do not belong to the same group. For example, a pencil, a pen, a ruler, an eraser, a chair are shown, the students separate educational tools, the chair is not part of the educational tools, it is called furniture. Such an exercise can also be carried out in the form of a game: certain words are given and it is required to find its superiority and explain why it is superior: swallow, sparrow, cat, music opposite conclusion: swallow, sparrow, nightingale - what about birds, chickens, roosters, turkeys? (birds) logical exercises should be meaningful, connect with students' experience, teach them to think correctly, clarify and systematize their knowledge.

Improving educational effectiveness by working with texts in mother tongue classes (PIRLS, PISA). The purpose of education in mother tongue classes is to develop speaking skills: to be able to understand the given information by listening; ability to understand information through writing; the ability to understand certain information by sight; ability to understand information through reading - listening comprehension - viewing comprehension - writing comprehension - reading comprehension. Uzbekistan is participating in the PIRLS-2025 evaluation system. PIRLS (Progress in international reading literacy study) is an international assessment system that evaluates the reading quality and comprehension levels of elementary school students. PISA (in English - the program of international student assessment) is a program that evaluates the literacy (reading, mathematics, natural sciences) and the ability to apply knowledge of 15-year-old students in different countries.

Reading literacy - is the student's ability to understand and respond to information provided in the form of a text, to be able to use the information read in the process of actively participating in the life of society, to increase knowledge and opportunities. Reading literacy is an assessment of the content of a given text, which includes excerpts from a given work of art, biography, letters, documents, articles from newspapers and magazines, the reader's understanding of the given text, reflection on its content. Charts, pictures, flashcards, graphs and tables to assess competencies such as being able to open a text and comment on what has been read.

PIRLS, PISA - texts: interesting creative texts of different content, according to the age characteristics of students; diagrams, pictures, maps, graphs and tables to explain the text; traditional books, magazines, documents and articles, excerpts from works of art, digital written forms. The following methods are used in creating text tasks: single-answer tests; multiple choice tests; answer questions briefly or in detail; questions about the cause of the event, explanation, creativity, making reports. Methods of working with the text: listening and understanding the text; reading and understanding the text; working with a dictionary; analysis of text content. Reading literacy - asking logical questions about the text - confirming theoretical knowledge based on the text - relying on knowledge and information outside the text.

Interactive technologies and methods of working with text: "modular learning" technology - "professional" method; "heuristic conversation" method; "mirror reflection" method; "investigator" method; "cognitive test" method; "conference" method. Technologies that develop reading literacy: work with text (story, novel, story) using the "modular learning" technology. The goal of "modular learning" technology: students are given the opportunity to read large texts or fragments of works; in a short period of time, such skills as familiarization with the text, oral and written speech, independent thinking, creativity, and cooperation are formed.

"Modular learning" technology implementation procedure: text, work parts are divided into parts and distributed to groups; Each group performs its part according to teacher's instructions. Thus, through group activities, the text is rounded; all students participate. Mastering a text or a work is realized in a short time.

"Professional" method: purpose: to teach students to think freely, independently, logically, and to speak in a coherent manner. Task: to teach students to work in groups, to explain and prove their opinions to group members. procedure for performing the "professional" method: a small group consists of 4-5 students; all team members work on the new text. In a group, students divide the text (narration, story) into parts.

Study assignments are prepared for each section, which students must complete. The procedure for implementing the "expertise" method: each group of students becomes an "expert" in their department by completing one of these tasks. Meetings of "experts" in each group will be held in reconstituted groups. These groups should have an "expert" in each part. "experts" share their knowledge one by one and explain it to their friends.

task for the "professional" method: - tell me, grandfather, - asked Alisher, - where do you get fairy tales? - from the inkwell, son, from the inkwell. - How will you get them out of there, grandfather? - feather pen, grandson, pen with a pen. - like fishing from the river with a fishing rod? "No, my little one, you can't tell such a story," said grandfather. First you need to learn how to take the pen from the ink tank and transfer it to the notebook: first hooks, then letters, then words. After that, a fairy tale may appear. The procedure for the implementation of the "professional" method was adopted in the 1st grade of school. He began to learn to read and write. First he learned to write hooks, letters, and then words. Alisher practiced a lot, but the fairy tale did not come out. - why, grandfather, I can't write a fairy tale? Or is the ink I'm using old? Or is my pen thin? - don't worry, Alisher! - comforted grandfather. - the time will come - you will learn to write not only fairy tales, but even bigger works... For that, read a lot of books, your mind will expand and you will reach your goal. Alisher was young and did not understand everything, but his grandfather warned him to remember what he said in the future.

Questions and tasks from the text task 1

1. Is the name of the boy in the story Alisher? Yes no
2. Did the child not have difficulty in making up a fairy tale from an inkwell? Yes No
3. Is drawing a fairy tale with ink like fishing? Yes no
4. Couldn't the child write a fairy tale because the ink was old? Yes no
5. What did grandfather tell Alisher about avoiding people? Yes no

Task 2 Should everyone have their own motto? Write your answer.

Task 3: correct the order of the story? 1. Grandfather told Alisher a fairy tale. 2. Alisher remembered his grandfather's words. 3. Alisher tried to write a fairy tale. 4. Alisher studied at school and learned to write.

Task 4: How do you convey the words of wisdom you heard from your grandfather to your friends? Explain in two sentences. Write your answer.

Task 5: if the story was written in the 21st century, what modern words would you replace the words "pen", "ink" with? Write your answer.

Task 6: in which answer is the proverb expressing the main idea of the story? A. is not written with a pen, it is written with the mind. B. You can't catch fish easily from the pond. C. Good luck D. Books are treasures, knowledge is wealth.

"Heuristic conversation" method. In this method, students look at pictures and find proverbs. The thought expressed in the proverb is clarified, students think logically. Check: 1. Male-female double bull. 2. If there is no wind, the tip of the tree will not move. 3. Don't get a gold, get a blessing. 4. The camel dreamed of a bath. 5. Don't go back on your word, follow the lion.

"Reflection in the mirror" method • in this method, students have to imagine themselves as if they are standing behind a mirror, where everything is said to be upside down. The inscriptions are also written from right to left, not from left to right. These posts are not easy to read. Therefore, students should read and interpret the given text quickly and correctly. • the teacher comments and evaluates the opinions and conclusions expressed by the students. My face, my face, answer without hiding! Who is the author of "Shum Bala"? Click on the question mark and read the correct answer.

"Investigator" method: the goal is to teach students to think freely, critically, to search, to find a solution to the problem based on the topic of the text through the method of summarizing and comparing thoughts. The task is to make a necessary conclusion or decision, to influence the team with one's opinion, to confirm it, to use the knowledge gained in solving a given problem. "investigator" method: students are distributed papers with the names of various characters in the work or story, words related to the characters.

Members of each group should read the name of the character of the work or the story on a piece of paper and express their opinion about the character of the work. The teacher comments on the opinions and conclusions expressed by the groups and evaluates the students. "Task according to the investigative method: students are given the writer's biography or the writer's works, poems or stories mixed with the works of other writers. Students have to find the works or poems of their chosen authors from the following answers: it is necessary to find a poem of the work of one writer or poet from a sheet with the name of mixed works.

CONCLUSION.

Recommendations: formation and development of skills to find open and closed information from texts. Changing the content of tasks. "when?", "where?" instead of such tasks, use tasks such as "why?", "explain the reason", "prove the answer". Use different forms of text in group activities and additional activities. Form the ability to work with single and multi-source texts. "Cognitive test" method. Use this method, words are created based on the given pictures.

Recommendations: development of students' ability to fully understand events, actions and consequences described in fiction; use of the teaching-methodical tool "assessment of reading literacy of primary school students in international subjects" during study hours outside the classroom; to develop students' skills to explain and coordinate ideas and information in the text with simple conclusions, to connect parts with common themes and ideas; development of students' reading skills in scientific, historical, geographical, social and other types of informational texts.

"Conference" method: the goal is to teach students to think freely, critically, to search, to find a solution to the problem related to the topic of the text, through the method of summarizing and comparing ideas. Task: teaches to make the necessary conclusion or decision, to influence the team with one's opinion, to confirm it, to use the acquired knowledge in solving the given problem. "happiness was in their hands, but..." - as an example - we compare the works "Eugene Onegin" by A. S. Pushkin and "Romeo and Juliet" by V. Shakespeare, "Farhad and Shirin" by Alisher Navai.

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